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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
- 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
- 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
- 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
- 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
- 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
- 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
- 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
- 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
- 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
- 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
- 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
- 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
- 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
- 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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COMMUNICATIVE LANGUAGE TEACHING IN MODERN CLASSROOMS: STRENGTHS, LIMITATIONS, AND PEDAGOGICAL IMPLICATIONS

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Abstract: Language acquisition is an ever-evolving process that requires a variety of approaches and methods for successful mastery. One of the primary reasons millions of people learn a second or foreign language is to communicate effectively across cultural and linguistic boundaries. In today's globalized world, English often serves as a lingua franca, facilitating international communication in education, business, and everyday interactions. This article explores Communicative Language Teaching (CLT), which remains one of the most influential methodologies in modern classrooms. CLT emphasizes real-world communication, learner autonomy, and authentic tasks over rote grammar drills, making it a powerful approach to developing communicative competence in diverse learning contexts. By examining its principles, benefits, and challenges, this study highlights the continued relevance of CLT in preparing learners to meet the demands of global communication.

Key words: language acquisition, approaches, communicative language teaching, communication, benefits, challenges.

Annotatsiya: Til o'zlashtirish doimiy ravishda rivojlanib boradigan jarayon bo'lib, uni muvaffaqiyatli egallash uchun turli yondashuvlar va metodlar talab etiladi. Millionlab odamlarning ikkinchi yoki chet tilini o'rganishining asosiy sabablaridan biri madaniy va lingvistik chegaralardan tashqarida samarali muloqot qilishdir. Bugungi globallashtirilgan dunyoda ingliz tili ko'pincha lingua franca sifatida xizmat qilib, ta'lim, biznes va kundalik muloqotda xalqaro aloqalarni osonlashtiradi. Ushbu maqolada zamonaviy sinflarda eng ta'sirchan metodologiyalardan biri bo'lib qolayotgan Kommunikativ til o'qitish (CLT) yondashuvi tahlil qilinadi. CLT haqiqiy hayotiy muloqotga, o'quvchi mustaqilligiga va autentik topshiriqlarga urg'u berib, grammatik mashqlardan ko'ra kommunikativ kompetensiyani rivojlantirishga samarali xizmat qiladi. Uning tamoyillari, afzalliklari va muammolarini tahlil qilish orqali ushbu tadqiqot CLTning global muloqot talablariga javob berishdagi dolzarbligini yoritadi.

Kalit so'zlar: til o'zlashtirish, yondashuvlar, kommunikativ til o'qitish, muloqot, afzalliklar, muammolar, kommunikativ yondashuv, kommunikativ kompetensiya.

Аннотация: Освоение языка – это постоянно развивающийся процесс, который требует разнообразных подходов и методов для успешного овладения им. Одной из основных причин, по которой миллионы людей изучают второй или иностранный язык, является стремление эффективно общаться за пределами культурных и языковых границ. В современном глобализированном мире английский язык часто выступает в роли lingua franca, облегчая международное общение в сфере образования, бизнеса и повседневной жизни. В данной статье рассматривается методика коммуникативного обучения языку (CLT), которая остаётся одной из наиболее влиятельных в современной образовательной практике. CLT делает акцент на реальном общении, автономии учащихся и аутентичных заданиях, а не на механическом выполнении грамматических упражнений, что делает её эффективным инструментом развития коммуникативной компетенции в различных учебных контекстах. Анализ её принципов, преимуществ и трудностей позволяет подчеркнуть сохраняющуюся актуальность CLT в подготовке учащихся к требованиям глобального общения.

Ключевые слова: освоение языка, подходы, коммуникативное обучение языку, коммуникация, преимущества, трудности, коммуникативный подход, коммуникативная компетенция.

INTRODUCTION

Language teaching has undergone numerous transitions through the implementation of different approaches over time. In particular, the teaching of English as a foreign language has long been at the center of worldwide attention. Early methods such as the Grammar Translation Method (GTM) and the Audio-Lingual Method were gradually replaced in the 1970s by the Communicative Language Teaching (CLT) approach, which emerged alongside Dell Hymes's (1972, pp. 69-93) concept of communicative competence. GTM proved ineffective in

language teaching because it focused solely on the mastery of grammatical competence (Richards, 2006, pp. 1-5). Students learned a language through rote learning and drills, both of which involved memorization rather than production.

In contrast, CLT includes a variety of aspects, such as knowing how to use language for many different purposes, using language appropriately in different contexts, shifting tone from informal to formal depending on the situation, and many others. CLT has transformed language classrooms from teacher-centered settings into student-centered ones. With this approach, students are more active, less afraid of making mistakes, and more responsible for their own learning. Teachers' roles have also shifted from their traditional positions to those of facilitators and moderators. Littlewood (2014, p. 7) describes the teacher's role as a "co-communicator" who supports learners in building meaningful communication.

The CLT framework has shaped curricula, classroom activities, and teacher training courses. Authentic materials such as newspapers, podcasts, and videos have replaced artificial textbook dialogues (Harmer, 2015, pp. 144-146). These real-life texts and tasks make learning more relevant and engaging. In this article, evidence from language teaching research and real-world classroom experience is used to explore the effectiveness of CLT, as well as its benefits and drawbacks. CLT has been widely praised for transforming language classrooms into learner-centered environments and for promoting authentic communication. At the same time, scholars have raised concerns about its limitations, particularly regarding grammatical accuracy, assessment challenges, and contextual constraints. In the following discussion, both the strengths and weaknesses of CLT are examined through research evidence and classroom practice in order to evaluate its overall effectiveness in foreign language education.

LITERATURE REVIEW

There are several advantages of CLT for both learners and teachers. Learners gain confidence in expressing ideas spontaneously, which enhances oral proficiency (Dos Santos, 2020, pp. 104-109). In this way, students learn to apply language in real-life contexts. According to Shehla Salmanova (2025, pp. 45-56), CLT focuses more on fluency, interaction, and authenticity in the target language than on drilling and grammatical accuracy. Moreover, this approach enhances creativity, critical thinking, and the use of language in real-life communication.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Although there are certain challenges and constraints associated with this approach, they are not insurmountable. There have been many initiatives aimed at improving teachers' skills and changing their perception of communicative teaching. Teachers should not be concerned about losing control over students (Littlewood, 2013, p. 5) if they manage to become facilitators rather than controllers of the learning process. In terms of large class size, this challenge can be overcome through group work and by assigning individual roles and responsibilities to each student while completing a group task.

By effectively integrating grammar into communication and finding a balance between fluency and accuracy, the shortcomings related to grammar can be minimized. Tongxin Zhang (2023, pp. 12-15) reports: "Teaching grammar in a CLT-based curriculum encourages authentic language use, balances accuracy and fluency, fosters learner autonomy, and aligns with modern language competence perspectives."

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

This approach enables students to simulate real conversations on different topics in the classroom environment through role plays, various projects, and group work. During this process, they apply grammar rules, new vocabulary, and, more importantly, practice communication. Drawbacks of CLT in modern classrooms. Although CLT offers a number of advantages, it also has its limitations. Firstly, it places limited emphasis on grammatical accuracy. Learners may develop fluency at the expense of accuracy. They may speak confidently but with persistent errors, such as misuse of verb tenses and subject-verb agreement problems.

Over time, these errors risk becoming fossilized, that is, habitual mistakes that are difficult to correct later. In academic or professional contexts, where precision matters, such as IELTS writing or formal presentations, this lack of accuracy can be a serious drawback. Secondly, there may be difficulties in assessment, as well as a lack of student motivation to build meaningful communication. According to Hyunjeong Nam (2023, pp. 76-77), there are several teacher-related and non-teacher-related constraints of CLT. Nam (2023, pp. 76-77) explains that the primary challenges are the lack of teacher training programmers, teachers' English proficiency, and teacher competence.

Other external factors that create challenges in the implementation of CLT are education policy, lack of resources, and classroom layout (Nam, 2023, p. 79). Lastly, English learners' low motivation to communicate and their limited communicative competence are seen as constraints of CLT (Wei et al., 2018, pp. 1-9). One reason for students' low motivation is that school assessments and university entrance examinations in many countries rely heavily on grammar tests.

CONCLUSION

In general, CLT has been proven to be one of the most effective approaches in modern language teaching. Although this method faces particular challenges, its potential advantages are far more significant for both learners and teachers. By integrating other approaches, communicative teaching can be further improved and innovated. At the same time, the future of CLT depends on how effectively educators and institutions address its limitations. A balanced integration of grammar instruction within communicative tasks can prevent the fossilization of errors and ensure that learners achieve both fluency and accuracy.

Moreover, assessment practices need to evolve in order to capture not only grammatical competence but also communicative ability, creativity, and critical thinking. Teacher training and professional development are equally crucial. As Nam (2023, p. 79) highlights, teachers' competence, proficiency, and access to resources directly influence the success of CLT. Therefore, investment in teacher education, curriculum design, and classroom infrastructure is essential to overcome contextual constraints.

Finally, CLT should not be viewed as a rigid method but as a flexible framework that can adapt to diverse educational contexts. When combined with evidence-based strategies, it empowers learners to become confident, globally minded communicators while maintaining linguistic accuracy. Thus, the future of foreign language education lies in a dynamic synthesis of communicative fluency, grammatical precision, and pedagogical innovation.

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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
 - 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
 - 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
 - 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
 - 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
 - 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
 - 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
 - 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
 - 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
 - 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
 - 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
 - 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
 - 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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